

The Impact of Safety and Health Measures of Employees at KJD Pharma Bidar

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Abstract- *The medication business in India was regarded at US\$33 billion of each 2017 and standard drugs address 20% of everything contemplated districts to the degree volume, making the country the best provider of nonexclusive designs generally. As displayed by the Department of Pharmaceuticals, Ministry of Chemicals and Fertilizers, neighborhood drug market turnover showed up at Rs 129,015 crore (US\$18.12 billion) in 2018, winding up being 9.4 percent year-on-year and affirmations pay was US\$17.28 billion in FY18 and US\$19.14 billion in FY19. Hyderabad, Mumbai, Pune, (Baddi, Himachal Pradesh), Chennai, Bangalore, Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Ankleshwar, Vapi, Sikkim and Kolkata are the key fix spot points of India. KJD pharm pvt. ltd, incorporated as a private limited company on 25th march 2014, an objective to manufacture, formulate, develop, refine, import, export all kinds of medicines, drugs and other related products.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The company had built its first manufacturing facility in 2016 at Naubad industrial area, Bidar to manufacture of pharmaceutical formulations i.e tablets, capsules, oral liquids and powder. The organization has technically qualified people in all the departments and good marketing network to deliver high level of customer service and reliability. New construction began in Jan 2016. First production scheduled for December 2017. \$8 million invested in new construction, new equipment's facility 45,000 square feet in size. Annual production of tablets 1 billion+doses, 24 million liquid bottles, 144million capsules. Bidar is city in the province of Karnataka, situated on the deccan level in north eastern piece of Karnataka. It is the head quarter of the Bidar locale what imparts its line to Maharashtra and Telangana. It is the northern most region of Karnataka. It is associated with NH9 and NH18 and entire city is coordinated with four path street and is around 666 km from state capital, Bangalore.

Company profile: KJD company is incorporated in the year mar 2014,25. The name of the company was declared as a company limited by shares and it is non govt. company. The authorized capital of the company was 4 crore and its paid up capital was invested nearly 2, 14, 76000. The general meeting was held in sep 30,2017. And the accounting year was 31, 2017.

This company manufactures tablets, capsules, syrups. With an objective of manufacturing, formulate, develop, refine, import and export, all medicines, drugs, and other related products. And the company is brain child of sri.kotarki and Deepak joshi.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

It is a business' obligation to ensure the wellbeing, security and government assistance of their workers and others who may be influenced by their business. Bosses should do whatever is sensibly practicable to accomplish this. Bosses have obligations to give a wellbeing and security measures to representatives at work environment.

2.1.1 Employee safety

Security of laborers alludes to the arrangement of a protected climate, safe hardware and safe methodology in the working environment to guarantee laborers' wellbeing and wellbeing. While associations unquestionably have an ethical commitment to guarantee the security of laborers, a dangerous working environment can likewise have genuine lawful and monetary ramifications for businesses. Wellbeing of laborers may likewise be known as specialist security or word related wellbeing and security. Each association ought to detail and execute a wellbeing strategy, the system to be embraced normally relies on the size of an organization, the quantity of plants it works, the idea of the business

where it is locked in, the creation innovation it utilizes, and the disposition of the administration.

After it has spelt out its wellbeing strategy, an organization ought to build up a security program, the essential objectives of which ought to be decrease the quantity of risky variables which are probably going to cause mishaps, and to foster safe working propensities among its representatives.

2.1.2 Employee health

Delegate prosperity is the headway and backing of the most broad degree of physical, mental and social flourishing of workers in all occupations by holding departures back from prosperity, controlling threats and adaption of work to people, and people to their positions.

HR specialists expect a huge part in ensuring laborer prosperity and security, as they most likely know the work space, the agents and their work demands. While HR specialists are not expected to know the particular pieces of workplace prosperity and security, they ought to acknowledge when and how to use existing resources for respond to agent concerns. In various affiliations, prosperity and security commitments are inside the HR division. To meet these commitments, HR specialists must.

- Understand the wellbeing and security duties of businesses, administrators, managers and workers inside the association.
- Implement faculty the board approaches to guarantee that everybody in the working environment knows about his/her obligations.
- Establish compelling methods of meeting wellbeing and security duties.
- Ensure that representatives satisfy their wellbeing and security duties as laid out in the authoritative strategies and projects. This guide gives general rules to incorporating working environment wellbeing and security in HR the board rehearses which incorporate.
- Preventing business related wounds and diseases.
- Fostering a work environment wellbeing society in which representatives and their directors cooperate to guarantee work environment security.

- Establishing managerial strategies that urge representatives to report dangerous conditions and hazardous practices to their administrators unafraid of being focused.
- Developing fitting recruiting, preparing and execution evaluation rehearses.
- Recruiting and holding the best representatives who care about their own prosperity and the prosperity of colleagues.

2.1.3 Employee safety

Each association ought to define and carry out a wellbeing strategy, the methodology to be embraced normally relies on the size of an organization, the quantity of plants it works, the idea of the business wherein it is locked in, the creation innovation it utilizes, and the disposition of the administration.

After it has spelt out its security strategy, an organization ought to set up a wellbeing program, the essential objectives of which ought to be diminish the quantity of risky variables which are probably going to cause mishaps, and to foster safe working propensities among its representatives.

Representative wellbeing is the advancement and support of the most significant level of physical, mental and social prosperity of laborers in all occupations by keeping takeoffs from wellbeing, controlling dangers and adaption of work to individuals, and individuals to their positions.

2.1.4 Objectives of safety and health

- Establish an unmistakable wellbeing and security focuses across the organization to empower execution to be estimated.
- Maintain a powerful wellbeing and security the executives framework in the organization.
- Raise representatives wellbeing and security mindfulness, and give preparing so they can securely complete, their duty.
- Minimize wellbeing and security occurrences.
- Provide data to help interview with every one of those keen on the wellbeing and security strategies, plans and execution of the organization.
- Promote the selection of wellbeing and security the board rehearses by the organization's project workers.

2.1.5 Principles of safety and health management system

- Before each action, consider how your behavior impacts your own and your colleague’s safety.
- Apply lockout tag out (LOTO) procedure and required permits to work.
- Comply with site restriction (smoking, alcohol, illegal substance etc).
- Use the requested personal protective equipment (PPF).
- Keep the fire system and emergency exists clear and ready to be used at all times.
- Respect speed limits for forklifts and watch out for pedestrians.
- Label, store and handle chemicals appropriately and limits the quantity to what is necessary.
- Ensure all machinery is secured and safe before starting to work.
- Before waste of disposal, strive to reduce, reuse or recycle material and use appropriate containers.

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

- Company has to provide a daily medical screening for employees.
- Cleaning work area and surface regularly.
- Company has to offer several lunch periods to reduce overcrowding.(in case of viral disease for ex: Covid-19)
- Emphasizing to employees the importance of frequent hand washing and make sanitizers containing easily available throughout the workplace.

3.2 Objectives of study:

- To study the wellbeing and security measures received in KJD Pharm privately owned business.
- To study the attention to the laborers about wellbeing and security in the work environment.
- To study the part of the executives in carrying out wellbeing and security.
- To study fulfillment level of the respondent's towards wellbeing and security measures.
- To study the association about and improvement level of wellbeing and security of representatives.

3.3 Need of study:

- Safety and health of employees important for the wellbeing of an employees and employers
- It is important for reduction of risks at workplace.
- Safety and health management programs can help you focus your efforts at improving work environment.
- When employers care about their employees, employees also take care about the company.
- Safety and health of employees can increase productivity level.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Table showing Impact of Employees Health on Productivity

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	32	80
Agree	7	18
Neutral	1	3
Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: KJD is pharmaceutical industry so, employees have to be conscious about their health as well as work productivity. 80% of employees strongly agreed towards health and productivity where as 18% employees only agreed towards health and productivity.

2. Table showing that do you get proper guidance from safety officer

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	21	53
Agree	17	43
Neutral	2	5
Disagree	0	0

Strongly Disagree	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: 53% of employees strongly agreed that they get a proper guidance from safety office where as 43% of employees only agreed towards guidance from safety officer.

3. Table showing opinion about Medical Facility Provided By Company.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Excellent	23	58
Good	12	30
Average	5	13
Bad	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: As KJD is chemical based industry, medical facilities are very much necessity so 58% of employees has an excellent opinion about medical facility where as 30% employees have good opinion and remaining employees have average opinion.

4. Table showing health insurance benefit provided by company.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	25	63
Agree	7	18
Neutral	3	8
Disagree	4	10

Strongly Disagree	1	3
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: As KJD is chemical based industry, employee's health will be at risk so health insurance benefit is necessary, 68% of employees strongly agreed towards insurance benefit, 18% employees only agreed and other rest employees have neutral opinion.

5. Table showing emergency safety tools available in your company premises.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Emergency Warning Bell	9	23
Emergency Signal	1	3
Emergency Exit Doors	2	5
All of the above	28	70
None	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: 70% of employees agreed that they have all the safety tools in there company. Safety tools are like emergency warning bell, signal and exit doors.

6. Is company providing first-aid box in every working room.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Yes	40	100
No	0	0

Grand Total	40	100%
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Interpretation: As KJD is manufacturing industry so first aid box is necessary at workplace, all 100% of employees agree that they have proper first aid box and first aid facility.

7. Table showing awareness about the company safety measure?

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Range 1-25	3	8
Range 26-50	6	15
Range 51-75	20	50
Range 76-100	11	28
Not at all	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: As it is a chemical based industry, employees must have awareness of safety measures at workplace. 50% of employees have knowledge about range of 51-75 and 28% of employees have knowledge about range of 76-100 and remaining employees have less than 50% knowledge.

8. Table showing health advantage given by the organization to the workers and their family.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	22	55
Agree	16	40
Neutral	1	3
Disagree	1	3
Strongly Disagree	0	0

Grand Total	40	100%
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Interpretation: As KJD is chemical based industry, employee's health will be at risk so health advantage benefit is necessary, 55% of employees strongly agreed towards health advantage benefit, 40% employees only agreed and other rest employees have neutral opinion.

9. Table shows provisions to specially abled employees.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	18	45
Agree	18	45
Neutral	4	10
Disagree	0	0
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: As KJD is chemical based industry, 45% of employees strongly agreed that company have provisions to special abled employees.

10. Table showing responsibility of management towards employees during working time.

Option	Responses	Performance in %
Strongly Agree	24	60

Agree	13	33
Neutral	2	5
Disagree	1	3
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Grand Total	40	100%

Interpretation: 60% of employees strongly agreed that management will take responsibility of employees during working time.

V. FINDINGS

- From the study, it was found that majority of the employees satisfied with Health and Safety benefit provides by the company.
- From the study, it was found that 44% respondents have an Excellent opinion about Medical Facility given by the company.
- From the study, it was found that No any respondents had bad opinion about Medical Facility given by the company.
- From the study, it was found that 44% of respondents make use of medical Examination conducted by the comp-any.
- From the study, it was found that 56% of respondents attended Safety and recommendation program.
- From the study, it was found that 48% of respondents satisfied with working environment of the Company.
- From the study, it was found that 54% of the respondents agreed that they get proper Safety guidance from Safety Officer.
- From the study, it was found that majority of employees said that wearing of white apron is compulsory for while working.
- From the study, it was found that 58% respondents said that very frequently the company had provided safety measures to the employees.

- From the study, it was found that 50% respondents told that the company will provide Health Insurance Benefit.
- From the study, it was found that 86% respondents said that the company organizes Safety and Health program for employees.

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study the following suggestions have been made:

- It is suggested that company need to provide attractive Rest Room facility.
- It is better to provide frequent Health and Safety training, at least once in a year.
- Safety committee has to be formed to monitor the health and safety issues.
- Company need to provide effective and proper guidance from safety officer.
- It is better to make aware about safety measures policies to employees.
- It is better to provide first aid box in every working room because as it is chemical industry.
- It is better to record the health care data of employees.
- It is better suggested that the company needs to give the quality of personal protection in company.

CONCLUSION

It is revealed from the study that, the health and the safety measures adapted according to the chemical factory policies. And it is reveals that awareness of the workers about health and the safety policies is only average. The role of management in implementation and the following safety rules is very effective. Most of the workers were satisfied with the health and safety environment of the company.

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